

The Effect of Agile Leadership and Work Environment to Employees' Performance in a VUCA World (Study on Millennial Generation Employees in Jabodetabek)

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ABSTRACT: The uncertainty situation that happened lately, especially these last two years, has forced all organizations to adapt and change fast. The ability of leaders to be more agile in doing the changes is needed. The changes needed not only to give new directions for the organization, but also to improve employees' performance especially the millennials. Furthermore, work environment is also a factor that determine how millennial employees' performance performed in organization. This research aims to analyze the agile leadership style and work environment will affect millennial employees' performance in a VUCA World that filled with volatility and uncertainty. The population for this research is millennial generation employees at Jabodetabek dan the sample selection was done using Hair Method. This paper was using PLS as the method for data analysis. The result showed that there was positive and significant influence for agile leadership and work environment to performance of millennial employees.

KEYWORDS: Agile Leadership, Work Environment, Employees' Performance, VUCA

I. INTRODUCTION

Beginning of year 2020, Indonesia was shocked by the existing of pandemic called COVID-19 that bring impact not only to the health of the people but also to other sectors. Until second semester 2021, the pandemic situation was even worst. The situation that happened not only caused the death of the people, but also the economic condition of the country. Companies faced challenges and tried to find their ways to survive. Lots of decisions need to be made, such as closing the business temporary and cutting or applying the unpaid leave for their employees. The business world is facing the situation where volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity is high. This situation we called a VUCA world. The industry 4.0 combined with VUCA world caused companies to think the strategies not only to survive, but also do some adjustments to the situation. So that they can sustain and grow. If companies cannot face and deal with the situation that happened, they might face difficulties and eventually will be closed.

For the companies to be able to survive and change their business model to face the VUCA situation, they need to make decisions, planning and manage their risk. They need to have attitude that they are ready to change. The changes might happen if only leaders in the organization have the ability of learning agility. Leaders who have learning agility are leaders who are willing and able to learn from the experiences they faced. They able to apply the learning to work in new condition (Eichinger et. al, 2013). Learning agility can also be defined as ability and willingness to learn from the current situation, then apply what it has learnt in the process of decision making to be success in new situation (De Meuse et.al, 2010). When a leader has an agile leadership skill, he can be flexible and lift the team abilities so that they can bring more contributions to the development of organization.

Oktariani et.al (2017) explained that the Y generations are tech savvy. They concerned to the use of technology in their work. They actively try the new things and more individualistic, egocentric, don't care and easy to get bored. The Y generation are also had low commitment dan loyalty to the company where they work. Y generation also known as millennial has high education and innovative. For the millennial, working is not the most important thing in. their lives. They like to find new opportunities. For the millennial, if they must work at the same place for longer time, the work that they do has to give them meaning and purpose (Lancaster, 2002). Cran (2014) stated that millennial will change their jobs at least twenty times in their lives compared to their previous generations. The millennial will stay at the company if they see their supervisor or teammate can act like their friend. When they don't like their leader, the millennial will quit from their jobs without a second thought. Seeing these unique characteristics of millennial and the VUCA situation, is a challenge for the organization and considering that millennial soon will become the biggest population in the organizations or companies.

The gap that exists between generation causes the traditional leadership style is no longer effective. There is a need to change from "boomer-centric" into "millennial-centric" work environment (Ferri-Reed, 2014). Kilber et.al (2014) mentioned that the

The Effect of Agile Leadership and Work Environment to Employees' Performance in a VUCA World (Study on Millennial Generation Employees in Jabodetabek)

argument aroused between generations need to be solved, by embracing the difference that come from the new generation. According to Rodriguez & Rodriguez (2015), challenges for the existing leadership situation (millennial and baby boomer or X generation) combined with the VUCA era, required wisdom or understanding and new leadership approach, especially for the senior level management. VUCA condition required specific leadership style, which is agile leadership style. This style will help to accelerate collaboration and eliminate communication bias for millennial and generations before them. This leadership style that is more collaborative will bring organization to be more innovative, flexible and enable them to make a right decision in this uncertain world (Rodriguez & Rodriguez, 2015).

Work environment has become important factor that determine the satisfaction and performance of employee. Nurisman (2018) mentioned there was a positive and significant influence of work environment toward job satisfaction. The finding from Siagian & Khair (2018) found that work environment has positive and significant influence towards employees' performance. The finding showed that better work environment will improve the performance of the employees.

This research article is expected to give a contribution to the topic related to Management study by analyzing how are the effect of Agile Leadership and Work Environment toward the performance of millennial employees.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee's Performance

Mangkunegara (2011), Hariandja (2002) and Rivai (2005) explained that employees' performance is the result of work that can be measured both in quality and quantity achieved by someone in a certain period of time, in the process of doing his work according to his responsibilities. According to Sedarmayanti (2011) performance is the system used to appraise and know if someone has done his work completely, or it can also be said that performance is the combination between work result (what people has to achieve) and competency (how that result achieved). Performance can also be defined as a result expected to be achieved by employee in optimum way (Robbins, 2006 & 2008).

Tjong & Siagian (2018) measure employees' performance by using five indicators, which are:

1. Quality

Measured from the employee's perception toward work quality they perform, skill of the employees in doing their work and their ability to finish the work.

2. Quantity

The number of units produced by employees and number of activities done by the employees

3. Efficient

Measure the level of activities that could be done on time, it is viewed from the coordination between output and being able to maximize the time available to do other activities

4. Effective

Level of the usage of organization resources such as manpower, money, technology and materials to produce output at optimum level

5. Independency

Independency is the level where employees able to do their work function according to the work commitment they make with the company and the responsibility of employees toward the company.

Agile Leadership

Agile leadership is the dynamic ability of a leader to feel and respond to the changes that happened in business environment by doing actions that focused, fast and flexible (Nick et. al, 2010). According to Neubauer et.al (2017), there are four competencies Agile Leader needs to have. Those are:

1. Humble

Humble is the ability to accept feedback and knowledge from others more experience than ourselves. In this era when the world changes so quick, knowing that we don't know is valuable as knowing what we know. Leaders need to learn the development of new knowledge that happened in the organization ecosystem. Agile leaders need to have willingness to learn and seek other advices both from inside or outside his organization. Agile leaders understand the importance to build the right team and retain his key persons who has talents next to him.

2. Adaptable

It is an acceptance knowing that changes are constant and to change our mind based on new information received is our strength and not weakness. The ability to adapt becomes more important in a complex and uncertain environment. Agile leaders adapt his behavior in short time based on his ability to make decision using the existing strong evidence. The rapid change of technology in this digital era need the ability to adapt for leaders. Agile leaders must know how to adapt themselves to face complexity and not resistance to change their way of thinking to face new information. Adaptability is the key to success both for organization and

The Effect of Agile Leadership and Work Environment to Employees' Performance in a VUCA World (Study on Millennial Generation Employees in Jabodetabek)

leader. Leaders need to embrace new ideas, change their believe if needed and communicate the changes direction to related stakeholders

3. Visionary

It is a long-term direction that is clear, even in short time uncertainty. It is important for leader to have clear vision for the future of his organization. In this rapid changes of technology and disruption against our business model, but at the same time the window of opportunity opened widely. It is important for leaders to have clear vision. A visioner leader will have ideas defined clearly to show direction where their organization should go, even though they are still not sure how to achieve. Strategies made by leader have changed from long term linear plans to be more agile plans.

4. Engaged

The willingness of leader to listen, interact and communicate with internal and external stakeholders combined with clear understanding what the trend are today. Clear articulation for vision and ability to adapt will help leader to recognize when action needs to be changed, is a competency that agile leader needs to have. Agile leader will always get involved to its consumer, partners, supplies, group member, staffs or other part involved in his business ecosystem. Agile leader is a leader who listen and communicate. They spend lots of time to interact with outside world.

Work Environment

Work environment in a organization become important factor that need to be considered. Though work environment does not interact directly with the production process. Work environment will affect employees' performance. Monroe in Pavee (2004) defined work environment as a work and workplace that will affect the workers at the time, they do their work. Work environment is included relationship between supervisor and workmate, equality and agility, fitness at work and work control as personal. Sedarmayati in Singgih et.al (2020) explained that work environment is everything included tools and materials, environment where employees work, work method and work arrangement, either as individual or group. Jain & Kaur (2014) categorized work environment into three aspects which are: Physics, Psychology and social. Physical environment is the environment where someone is trying to adapt himself with his workplace. Physical environments consist of air circulation and room temperature, noise, lighting, and facility. Second aspect is psychology, it is the condition that someone experience such as tired, bored, behavior and attitude of workmate. Third aspect is social environment where someone interact with others. Social aspect consists of space needed, cleanliness and security.

Husain (2018) seen that the X and Y generation was looking for the work environment that fun and creative. They translated the work environment as an open space, can be trusted and an organization which gives sport facilities, game and entertainment. The quality of work environment influences the employee's behavior, productivity and satisfaction. Husain (2018) defined work environment as:

1. Open communication, how corporate communicates its vision and mission so employees can support those vision and mission
2. Work balance, a balance between corporate work and personal life
3. Consistency, to create a condition where leader is being responsible toward issues the corporate face

Millennial Generation

Strauss & Howe in Paramitha & Ihalauw (2018) mentioned that millennial generation or often called as Y generation is the generation that was born in the year 1982-2000. The millennials are known as a generation that has skills, experiences in high technology. Like to work in a group, having high level of creativity, friendly, open and easy to adjust themselves (Cran, 2014). Millennials have high self-confidence, able to work few things at the same times and always have high level of energy. They need social interaction and like to see instant result and drive by the need to be able to develop their career path in a fast pace. Millennials are more egocentric, individualist and easy to get bored. Dressing casually and relax are their outfit. Millennials grown during fast technology changes; therefore, they are not afraid with the changes. However, they are impatient to go through the process of the changes. At workplace, millennials like to get high position when they start their job. They are very competitive. Enjoy challenges and want to be acknowledge. They don't expect to work at the same level for long time. They like to work in different segment in the organization to see 'big picture' of the organization, so that they can make themselves worthy in organization (Ananatmula & Shrivastav, 2012). Millennials are not working to get their basic need, but to do something more meaningful for their live and others. They want to bring changes to the world (Espinoza et.al, 2015). Millennials have the tendency for not having work commitment and loyal when they work for a company (Oktariani et.al, 2017).

VUCA

In VUCA world, the social economic world is defined as the world that has volatility, uncertain, complex and ambiguity. Each characteristic will influence the success of organization. Tatiana (2019) explained the concept of VUCA as follow:

1. Volatility

The Effect of Agile Leadership and Work Environment to Employees' Performance in a VUCA World (Study on Millennial Generation Employees in Jabodetabek)

A situation described as volatile situation when there is not enough data to predict or expect one action that can be used or done effectively. When this situation happened, it will become a challenge for the organization to decide the direction for the changes. Volatile situation in VUCA world is like a storm. Even though scientist know this situation occurred and what kind of conditions companies faced to keep themselves survive and grow, but it is hard to predict how strong the company can grow (Schick et.al, 2017).

2. Uncertainty

It is the consequences for the difficulties that the company faced. The cause of the events and consequences might be predicted, but it is impossible to predict how that event will impact the future of the organization or if that situation is significant for the company to react or respond immediately. The uncertain situation gives a challenge to be able to identify the situations or events, therefore it is difficult to offer a concrete solution. The company does not know what the most effective solution is and for what kind of situation.

3. Complexity

It is the situation when the big picture of a situation or event becomes unclear or cannot be observed rightly. If the organization only focus on certain part. It will not be able to make the right decision. Organization need to be able to connect every parts to create the network of all information, procedures and actions.

4. Ambiguity

The last characteristics of VUCA is related to the increase of innovative solutions – in technology and information. Nowadays, making the decision based on past experiences are no longer relevant. Organization needs to be able to select the best options when some information is unclear.

Based on the introduction and literature review explained above, the hypotheses for this research are:

H1; Agile Leadership has effect on employee's performance

H2: Work Environment has effect on employee's performance

The research framework showed in Figure 1

Figure 1. Research Framework

III. METHOD

Population and Sample

The population for this research is millennial employees at Jabodetabek. The sample is collected by using Hair formula by collecting data from 60 respondents. Data was collected through questionnaires given to respondents.

Variable Operation

Variable Agile Leadership (X1) has the dimensions Humble, Adaptable, Visionary and Engaged

Variable Work Environment (X2) has the dimensions Physical Environment, Psychology Environment and Social Environment

Variable Employee's Performance (Y) has the dimension Quality, Quantity, Efficient, Effective, and Independency

Data Analysis

1. Descriptive Statistics

Used to analyze data by describing data to make general conclusions

2. Validity and reliability test

The purpose for this test is to know if all items in the questionnaires are valid and reliable. The test will use SPSS 21 and use Correlation Product Moment method.

The Effect of Agile Leadership and Work Environment to Employees' Performance in a VUCA World (Study on Millennial Generation Employees in Jabodetabek)

3. Hypothesis Test

This research uses SmartPLS to test the outer and inner model. Validity and reliability test for the model will use Composite Reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE). testing the hypothesis uses R^2 , F, Q^2 test.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics analysis is used to know the min, max and mean values for each variable. The mean value for Agile Leadership is 4.15. The value explained that respondents scored their leaders high for having Agile Leadership. For Work Environment mean value is 4.03. The value stated that respondents considered their organization has good work environment. The mean value for Employee's Performance showed 4.32. The result explained that respondents considered themselves for having good performance based on the measurement used.

Table 1. Mean and Standard Deviation values

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation
Agile Leadership	4.15	0.92
Work Environment	4.03	1.00
Employee's Performance	4.32	0.68

2. Outer and Inner Model Test

Using SmartPLS 3.0, tests were conducted to know the value of outer and inner model and testing the hypothesis. The result test for validity dan reliability test for model showed that all the indicators were valid and reliable. All the indicators showed outer loading > 0.7. Value of AVE > 0.5. The value for CR > 0.7, means that variables are reliable

Figure 2. Outer Model

Table 2. Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Notes
Agile Leadership	0.733	Valid
Work Environment	0.695	Valid
Employees' Performance	0.682	Valid

The Effect of Agile Leadership and Work Environment to Employees' Performance in a VUCA World (Study on Millennial Generation Employees in Jabodetabek)

Table 3. Composite Reliability

Variable	Composite Reliability	Notes
Agile Leadership	0.976	Reliable
Work Environment	0.965	Reliable
Employees' Performance	0.963	Reliable

a. R Square (R^2)

According to Ghozali & Latan (2014), value for R-square can be used to measure independent variable to dependent variable to see if the effect is substantive. Result for R^2 showed 0.399, means that Agile Leadership and Work Environment have effect on Employees' Performance in a moderate way.

Table 4. R^2

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Employees' Performance	0.399	0.378

b. Effect Size (F^2)

The value for effect size was used to evaluate if exogen variable was eliminate, it would give substantive effect to the endogen variable. The value showed that Agile Leadership and Work Environment have small effect toward Employee's performance.

Table 5. Effect Size (F^2)

	Employees' Performance
Agile Leadership	0.091
Work Environment	0.100

c. Predictive Relevance (Q^2)

Q-square measured how good the observation given by the model and parameter estimation. Q-square > 0 showed the model has predictive relevance

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Q-Square} &= 1 - [1 - R^2] \\
 &= 1 - [1 - 0.399] \\
 &= 1 - 0.601
 \end{aligned}$$

Q-Square = 0.399

From the result showed that the value was 0.399. This meant that 39.9% the model was explained by the diversity of the data and the other 60.1% was explained by other factors

d. Hypothesis Test

The testing for the hypothesis used the t-statistic co-efficient by using bootstrapping. Indicator that has t-statistics > 1.96 will be significant (Ghozali & Latan, 2014). Indicators also has an effect if the p-value < 0.05 (Haryono, 2017).

Table 6. Hypothesis Test

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values
Agile Leadership -> Employees' Performance	0.334	0.339	0.153	2.181	0.030
Work Environment -> Employees' Performance	0.349	0.382	0.138	2.527	0.012

The Effect of Agile Leadership and Work Environment to Employees' Performance in a VUCA World (Study on Millennial Generation Employees in Jabodetabek)

Figure 3. Inner Model

Based on Table 6, it could be concluded:

- 1) Hypothesis 1: Agile Leadership has effect on Employees' Performance
 Agile Leadership has t-statistic value 2.181 > 1.96; p-value 0.030 < 0.05 and original sample 0.334. Therefore, H₁ accepted, means that Agile Leadership has positive and significant effect on Employees' Performance
- 2) Hypothesis 2: Work Environment has effect on Employees' Performance
 Work Environment has t-statistic value 2.527 > 1.96; p-value 0.012 < 0.05 and original sample 0.349. Therefore, H₂ accepted, means that Work Environment has positive and significant effect on Employees' Performance.

V. DISCUSSION

Agile Leadership has positive and significant effect on Employees' Performance. It means that the changes of Agile Leadership will change the Employees' Performance at the same direction. In other words when the leader has more Agile Leadership ability, it will increase the employees' performance. In VUCA world that full of uncertainty, complexity and has high volatility, will require leaders to be agile and able to see the changes. Millennial employees think that having leaders who have clear vision and willing to change according to the changing of the world is very important. When the millennials lead by leaders who understand well their visions and able to adapt with changes that happened in VUCA era, will make the millennials able to perform their role at works just like what their supervisors want. Millennials will have high commitment toward the organization they work for. It happened because the millennials can see that the organization exist because it has purpose and it communicate clearly to the employees.

Work Environment has positive and significant effect on Employees' Performance. It means that the changes of work environment will change the employees' performance in the same direction. The result consistent with the research done by Nurisman (2018) and Siagian & Khair (2010) that showed work environment has positive and significant effect on employees' performance. VUCA era gives bigger opportunity for the millennials to search organization that can give them work environment where they can interact more with others. Technology helps the millennials work faster and give them more time to do other meaningful things. They expect to work in organization, in which the work environment will help them to achieve the best effort at work and receive acknowledgement from their leaders

The Effect of Agile Leadership and Work Environment to Employees' Performance in a VUCA World (Study on Millennial Generation Employees in Jabodetabek)

VI. CONCLUSION

1. This research concluded that Agile Leadership has effect on Employees' Performance. The value for path coefficient was 0.334 showed that agile leadership has positive and significant effect on employees' performance. This showed that millennial employees work at VUCA era are expecting to be led by leaders who are agile and able to adapt the changes. When employees see that the leaders have the ability like what they expected, it will affect how they perform their work and do what their organization wants them to do.
2. Work Environment has effect on Employees' Performance. The value for path coefficient was 0.349 showed that work environment has positive and significant effect on employees' performance. The better the work environment, employees' performance will increase. Millennials at VUCA world are looking for organization which can give them work environment to be able interact more with their friends and workmate. They expect that technology will help them to work faster so that they

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The Effect of Agile Leadership and Work Environment to Employees' Performance in a VUCA World (Study on Millennial Generation Employees in Jabodetabek)

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